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Forest cover controls on debris flow sediment connectivity in the Stolla Basin, Italy

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Abstract—Detailed knowledge of debris flow runout is essential for hazard mitigation – this study examines the influence of forest cover on debris flow runout and sediment connectivity in the Stolla basin, South Tyrol, Italy. An open-source Gravitational Process Path (GPP) model within SAGA GIS was used to simulate runout paths via a random walk algorithm, with distances constrained by Perla’s two-parameter friction model (PCM). Calibration was guided by two primary objectives: accurately reproducing all observed connected debris flows and minimizing the overall relative error across the region. To account for forest cover, we integrated a crown height model (CHM) derived from pre-event LiDAR data, for integrating spatially variable friction parameters. Our results show that incorporating forest cover considerably improves the accuracy of simulated runout paths and distances, especially in terms of sediment connectivity, while also revealing the trade-offs between optimizing for connectivity and reducing regional error.

I. INTRODUCTION

Debris flows are highly destructive natural hazards in mountainous regions, mobilizing large volumes of sediment and posing significant risks to ecosystems, infrastructure, and communities. Understanding debris flow runout is critical for assessing sediment connectivity, especially in river systems where these processes influence sediment delivery and deposition.

The purpose of this study is to explore the controlling impacts of forest cover on connectivity of debris flows to stream channel networks in the Stolla Basin, South Tyrol, Italy. This study calibrates a process-based runout model in the Stolla basin to

optimize connectivity predictions while minimizing errors. It integrates forest cover to refine spatially variable friction parameters and improve the model’s representation of debris flow dynamics. The model is validated by comparing predicted and observed connectivity for both connected and non-connected debris flows. By incorporating forest cover into the modeling framework, this research aims to advance the understanding of debris flow sediment transport and connectivity in forested mountain landscapes.

II. STUDY AREA

The Stolla Creek basin, located in eastern South Tyrol, Italy spans 40 km² and ranges in elevation from 1185 m at its outlet to 3146 m at its highest peak. Formerly glaciated during the Pleistocene, the catchment now receives 860 mm of mean annual precipitation and has a mean annual temperature of 5.5 °C [1]. The 11.5 km-long Stolla Creek flows into the Prags/Braies River, a tributary of the Rienz/Rienza within the Etsch/Adige river basin. Vegetation includes conifer forests (48%), primarily Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and silver fir (*Abies alba*), up to the 2200–2300 m tree line, transitioning to grasslands (15%) and shrublands (11%) dominated by mugo pine (*Pinus mugo*) at higher elevations. Unvegetated areas, comprised of bedrock and sediments, account for 26% of the basin [1].

This analysis focuses on more than 600 debris flows that were triggered in the Stolla basin during a 2017 extreme rainfall event. The complete runout (source to deposition area) of the flows were mapped using high-resolution aerial imagery and LiDAR data [1].

III. METHODS

A. GPP Runout Modelling

The Gravitational Process Path (GPP) [2] model was used to regionally simulate runout for the purpose of exploring process-based characteristics controlling connectivity to the main river channel in the Stolla basin. The GPP model is an open-source framework in the SAGA-GIS software that provides users with various model components to simulate runout path, distance, velocity and deposition of material of mass movements.

Runout path was modelled using the random walk process path component of the GPP model. Random walks model the potential paths of runout by iteratively simulating (via Monte Carlo simulation) the downslope movement path of debris flows originating in an individual source-area grid cell. This simulation results in a grid with runout frequencies that indicate how many times a grid cell has been traversed. There are three parameters that need to be calibrated to obtain a desired runout path: (1) a slope threshold ($^\circ$) defining where divergent flow is allowed; (2) the exponent of divergence that controls the amount of divergence, or lateral spreading; and (3) a persistence factor that controls the direction of movement [2].

Runout distance was constrained using Perla's two-parameter friction model (PCM) component of the GPP model. It is a center-of-mass model where motion is controlled by (1) the sliding friction coefficient and (2) the mass-to-drag ratio. The sliding friction coefficient μ controls the velocity of movement and the mass-to-drag ratio M/D (m) controls velocity movement over steep terrain [2].

To simulate runout on a regional scale, the runout path and distance needs to be calibrated. This was done using the runoptGPP R package [3]. First the path was calibrated by finding optimal random walk model parameters based on a random sample of 100 debris flows across the entire Stolla basin using 1000 walks per source cell. Runout path was calibrated using two approaches in this work: (1) calibrating the model for connectivity and (2) for the entire region. Please see Goetz et al (2021) for more optimization procedure details.

Source areas for each event were automatically selected by selecting the cells within the top 5% elevations for each observed runout path. The runout modelling was performed on a 5 x 5 m spatial resolution sink-filled digital terrain model (DTM). The DTM was sink filled to help simulate the infilling process that can occur during a debris flow event.

B. Calibrating for connectivity and relative error

The PCM model was optimized to find the μ and M/D values with lowest relative error that also resulted in all observed connected debris flows simulated as connected. The objective of this approach was to ensure that the calibrated model is capable of simulating events that connect to the main river channel. In

contrast, when optimizing the regional model for higher performance, it is likely that larger debris flow events that reach the river are underestimated, since they usually have much lower μ than medium to small debris flows.

Additionally, several models were calibrated using subsets of only the connected debris flows, the not connected debris flows and all the sampled debris flows. This allowed for comparison in performance to previous approaches for regional model calibration [3].

C. Accounting for forest cover in the GPP model

The pre-event forest conditions were based on a crown height model (CHM) computed from a 1 m resolution DTM and digital surface model (DSM) surveyed in 2010 (Eqn. 1), which was resampled to 5 m spatial resolution.

$$CHM = DSM - DTM \quad (1)$$

To ensure that the differences in the CHM were only attributed to changes in vegetation and not artefacts in steep terrain, a land cover map was used to mask out elevation changes detected in non-vegetation classes (e.g. loose debris and outcrops).

The pre-event forest conditions were introduced into the GPP model by creating grids for μ and M/D values, where grid cells that contained forest were assigned higher μ and lower M/D values, which reduce runout distance due to higher friction and lower runout velocities, respectively. The values assigned to forest and non-forest areas were based on optimal parameter sets determined for the connected debris flow events and across the entire region. This is illustrated in the following equations,

$$\mu_i = \begin{cases} \mu_{conn}A_i, & \text{if } A_i = 0; \\ \mu_{relerr}A_i, & \text{if } A_i = 1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and

$$M/D_i = \begin{cases} M/D_{conn}A_i, & \text{if } A_i = 0; \\ M/D_{relerr}A_i, & \text{if } A_i = 1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where μ_i and M/D_i are parameters at grid cell locations i , μ_{conn} and M/D_{conn} are optimal global parameter sets for connected runout events, μ_{relerr} and M/D_{relerr} are optimal global parameter sets that resulted in the lowest median relative errors for all sampled runout events, and A_i is forest cover. $A_i = 1$ are grid cells classified with forest and $A_i = 0$ are grid cells without forest cover. The final parameters for Equations 2 and 3 were determined by a trial-and-error approach and visual inspection of the simulated runout paths. The calibrated parameters from the connectivity optimization and lower median relative error served as a starting point in parameter testing.

D. Model sample and validation

To reduce computational time during the exhaustive grid search optimization procedure a subsample of the Stolla basin runout tracks was sampled below a tree line (< 2100 m.a.s.l.) In

total 154 debris flows were sampled of which 22 were classified as connected to the Stolla basin river channel.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Crown height modelling

The resulting crown height modelling illustrates much higher and denser forest cover in the north-western and east hillslopes in the Stolla basin. When testing for a suitable crown height model cut-off for spatial modelling of μ and M/D , it was found that simulated runout behavior of debris flows appeared most similar to the observed events when areas with a crown height > 10 m was used (Fig. 1). This threshold provided “openings” in the forested landscape where simulated debris flows could follow observed debris flow paths. Lower thresholds often resulted in closing these “openings”, which prevented simulated debris flows from connecting to the main river channel.

B. Parameter calibration and validation

The optimal parameters for ensuring all observed connected debris flows were simulated as connected were $\mu = 0.04$ and $M/D = 55$. The optimal parameters for a model trained to minimize the median relative error with all the sample debris flows were a $\mu = 0.38$ and $M/D = 35$. It is evident that the μ values are much higher when training the model with all sampled data. This higher μ results in overall lower simulated runout lengths, which can result in under predicting the number of debris flows that connected to the river channel.

The median relative errors were low (0.06 and 0.10) for GPP models that were independently calibrated for minimizing the relative error for connected and non-connected debris flows compared to the globally calibrated model (0.33). This result hints that there could be spatial attributes, such as terrain conditions, forest cover, available source material, that account for the differences in optimal μ .

Calibrating for connectivity came at the cost of reducing the overall performance of simulated connected debris. That is, debris flow lengths were either similar to the observed length or overestimated. When using the median relative error approach for optimization with only connected debris flows, the overall median error was reduced (0.06 vs. 0.17), however this came at the cost of underestimating the length of some debris flows, including ones that were observed to connect with the main river channel.

Figure 1. Map of crown height model and cutoff/threshold > 10 m.

The performance of the calibrated parameters was assessed using the median relative error of observed runout length and simulated/estimated runout length. These lengths were computed using the minimum area bounding box method [3]. To gain insights on how the model performs for connected and non-connected debris flows, the performance was estimated for data subsets containing (1) only the debris flows that connected to the main channel, (2) only the debris flows that did not connect to the main channel, and (3) all of the debris flows in the sample. The performance was also qualitatively explored for geomorphic plausibility by visual inspection of the corresponding simulated runout maps for individual events and the regionally applied models.

Figure 2. Maps of simulated runout paths for each event in the Stolla basin. (A) μ and M/D globally optimized for connectivity, and (B) spatial varying μ and M/D ratio to account for forest cover influence.

Overall, the GPP model calibrated to minimize the relative error of connected debris flows had the best performance in terms of lowest median relative error, followed by the spatial μ and M/D model that accounted for forest cover, and then the model calibrated for connectivity. The model that accounted for forest cover was able to decrease the overall median relative error of the calibrated for connectivity model by 30% (Fig. 2B). It also managed to simulate 22/22 connected debris flows as connected. Through visual inspection, the model with forest cover appears to perform better at matching the observed runout paths, particularly in forest areas, compared to the model calibrated for connectivity.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the calibration for connectivity GPP model in the Stolla basin does perform well at simulating connected slides but comes at the cost of over predicting the runout lengths of non-connected debris flows. The connected debris flows tended to have low sliding friction coefficients compared to non-connected. Typically, larger events were related to lower sliding coefficients, which hints that regional GPP modelling can be improved by better representing the controls of runout length (e.g. catchment area, source areas size, and presence of forest in the runout path) in a model with spatially varying parameters.

The best connectivity results were obtained using a spatial model of the runout parameters that considered forest cover. This indicates that the distribution of forest does play an important role in debris flow sediment transport connectivity in this basin. Likely, changes in the forest cover would result in increased sediment transport to the main river channel.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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